

Zn, Sb, Pb (Au) Mineralization of Hammam N'bails, NE of Algeria

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Abstract : Polymetallic mineralizations with Zn, Sb, Pb boxed in miopliocene limestones of Hammam N'bails's basin are regarded as the youngest mineralizations of North East of Algeria and are characterized by the presence of rather rare mineral phases throughout the world such as nadorite and flajolotite. Mineralization seems to have a bond with thermal springs emergent within the basin and with the faults which limit the basin. The comparison between mineralizations and similar ore deposits known in the world and which are characterized by the presence of the noble metals such as gold and the discovery of traces of this metal (1.4g/t) enables us to start again the problems of the noble metals of the type "low sulfidation" related to the thermal springs in the area in particular and in all Algerian North generally.

Keywords : Nadorite, galana, gold, dolomitisation, epigenetic, hot springs, , miopliocene, Hammam N'bails, algeria

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